

VARIABILITY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract. *This article discusses about the internal classification of variability of phraseological units that are considered lexical variation within them.*

Key words: *Variation, criterion, phraseological units, speech, norm, semantic variation.*

ВАРИАБЕЛЬНОСТЬ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ

Аннотация. *В данной статье речь идет о внутренней классификации вариативности фразеологических единиц, которые считаются лексической вариативностью внутри них.*

Ключевые слова: *вариация, критерий, фразеологизмы, речь, норма, семантическая вариация.*

INTRODUCTION

According to the feature of expressing the lexical meaning, the variability of the phraseological units are distinguished by their uniqueness, including lexical variations as well. The issue of phraseological variation in Uzbek linguistics was specially studied in the researches of Professor Sh. Rakhmatullaev. "Variantization is a phenomenon that belongs to all language units (including phonemes), especially phraseological units. Two and three-variable phraseological units set up the main part of multi-variant idioms. In general, variation is more common in phraseological units than other language units, the number of variants of one idiom can reach to ten.

The scientist gives valuable information about the specific features of variability of phraseological and the criteria for determining variants:

"Combining several variations of a particular phraseological unit into one can figure out the following:

- a) due to various changes, one of them grew out of the other, all of them merged into one source;
- b) based on the same image (regardless of whether this image fades or not according to options);
- c) mean the same dictionary meaning (regardless of whether there is a difference in the edge of mutual meaning, speech, stylistic sign);
- g) the presence of a common word-component in the composition of mutually grown options".

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

It is true that the integrity of the lexical meaning of the phraseological units does not change when it changes from variant to variant. The differences in the form of the options will not reach the level of quality. The amount of exchange of words or other means in the form is not enough to affect the essence of the phrase. Such a quantitative change will not reach a certain standard level. If the quantitative change goes beyond the standard line, it goes to the limit of the qualitative change.

It seems that when separating and interpreting variants of phraseological units and other linguistic units, distinguishing them from other related phenomena (e.g., synonyms,

graduonyms), the transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes is considered to be a manifestation of the dialectical law in language, it is appropriate to adhere to linguistic gradation, which fulfills the task of linguistic methodology .

Sh.Rakhmatullaev differs phraseological units into the following ones:

- a) lexical variation;
- b) grammatical variation.

"The variation formed by changing the component represented by the word of an independent category in the structure of the phrase is called a lexical variant. In this case, the word-component will be:

- a) replaced; b) added; c) removed.

The most complicated of these is variation based on lexical substitution.

The scientist claims that the composition of phraseological units is dominated by semantic relationships between interchangeable words.

Interchangeable words in the composition of variant phraseological units have a semantic relationship. Examples of this include:

to 'rt tomoni qibla – to 'rt tarafi qibla (tomon – taraf)
otimni boshqa qo 'yaman – nomimni boshqa qo 'yaman (ot – nom)

RESEARCH RESULTS

In addition to the replacement of synonymous words, there are also variant phraseological units that differ in denotative meaning to a certain extent, but are different in meaning. Sh. Rakhmatullaev considers it as a variant phraseological unit that is formed by the exchange of words with close meaning. We prefer to refer to them as variant phrases based on the exchange of denotative graduonyms.

For instance:

ikki qo 'lini og 'ziga tiqmoq – ikki qo 'lini og 'ziga solmoq (tiqmoq – solmoq)
ikki qo 'lini burniga suqib – ikki qo 'lini burniga tiqib (suqmoq – tiqmoq)

It can be seen that there are subtle semantic differences in the meanings of such variant phraseological units.

Variant idioms can also be formed based on phraseological contraction, that is, the omission of some words in the phrases. This phenomenon can be called the elliptical method of the formation of variants. Here are some examples:

daryodan bir tomchi – daryodan tomchi
qo 'lini yuvib qo 'ltiqqa urmoq – qo 'lni qo 'ltiqqa urmoq
haddidan oshirib yubormoq – haddidan oshmoq

Among the phraseological units, there are also variations that differ due to grammatical forms. They can also be divided into the following types:

- a) variant phraseological units with changed grammatical form;
- b) variant phraseological units with added grammatical form;
- c) variant phraseological units with an omitted grammatical form;
- g) variant phraseological units with a changed grammatical order.

The following can be samples for variant phraseological units with a changed grammatical form:

ko 'zini pishirdi – ko 'zini pishitdi (orttirma nisbat – orttirma nisbat; 'subject + have + object + past participle')

pinagini buzmaslik – pinak buzmay (harakat nomi – ravishdosh shakli; gerund-participle)
sirkasi suv ko'tarmaydi – sirkasi suv ko'tarmaydigan – sirkasi suv ko'tarmas (sof fe'l shakli – sifatdosh – sifatdosh; non-finite-past participle- past participle)

DISCUSSION

Samples for variant phraseological units with added grammatical form:

yuzaga chiqmoq – yuzaga chiqarmoq (aniq nisbat – orttirma nisbat; active voice-have smth done)

holdan toymoq – holdan toydirmoq (orttirma nisbat; have smth done)

ko'ngli bo'shadi – ko'ngli bo'shashdi (birgalik nisbat; cooperative action)

bahrini ochmoq – bahri ochilmoq (majhul nisbat; passive voice)

kun o'tkazmoq – kunini o'tkazmoq (tushum kelishigi; accusative case)

yaqin olmoq – yaqinroq olmoq (orttirma daraja; superlative form)

ko'ngil yozmoq – ko'nglini yozmoq (egalik shakli, tushum kelishigi; possessive case-accusative case)

ko'ngli keng – ko'ngil keng bo'lsa (bog'lama; subjunctive mood)

Variant phraseological units with an omitted grammatical form have nominal grammatical categories and the linguistic norms will be based on it. Here are some examples:

asabiga tegmoq – asabga tegmoq (egalik shakli; possessiveness)

jonini fido qilmoq – jon fido qilmoq (egalik shakli va tushum kelishigi; possessiveness and accusative case).

In variant phraseological units based on the change of grammatical order, the words in the phrase change their place, but the semantic meaning remains in any occasions. For example:

og'zing qani desa qulog'ini ko'rsatmoq – qulog'ing qani desa og'zini ko'rsatmoq

san-manga bormoq – man-sanga bormoq

Variation of phraseological units based on the change of grammatical order are divided into two:

a) change of grammatical order is determined by the speech structure of the sentence;

ko'ngli qattiq – qattiq ko'ngil

ko'z yummoq – yumilgan ko'z (ko'ra bila turib e'tiborsiz qoldirmoq)

b) change of grammatical order is not connected to the speech structure of the sentence;

astar-avrasini ag'darmoq – avra-astarini ag'darmoq

ignasidan ipigacha – ipidan ignasigacha

CONCLUSION

It is characterized by a relatively small number of variant phraseological units that have arisen based on the change of the linguistic order of the word chain in its composition. First of all, it is characterized by the fact that phraseological units have a stable construction nature. At the same time, it strengthens, clarifies the meaning conveyed from the phraseological unit. Furthermore, phraseological units increase the expressiveness and colorfulness of the speech.

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